

Characteristics of cutaneous manifestations and hematological parameters in coronavirus infection

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In December 2019, cases of pneumonia of unknown origin were reported in Wuhan, China. These were subsequently found to be caused by a new pathogen, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), isolated from the lower respiratory tract of affected patients.

This is the third time in the last few decades that a coronavirus endemic in animal species has made the jump to humans.¹ Prior to these jumps, coronaviruses (HCoV) alfa (HCoV-229E and HCoV-NL63) and beta (HCoV-JHKU1, HCoV-OC43) had been identified as endemic in humans. In 2002, there was an outbreak in China of a coronavirus that caused severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS). The virus was named SARS-CoV, and mortality was reported at around 10%. In 2012, a respiratory syndrome caused by a coronavirus from the Middle East (MERS-CoV) was identified in Saudi Arabia. In this case, the mortality was 35%. SARS-CoV-2 is the new member of this group. Disease associated with the virus is denoted coronavirus disease-19 (COVID-19), thus avoiding any geographical qualification. The virus propagated out of control and the outbreak was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO) in March 2020.

The most frequent manifestations of infection with SARS-CoV-2 include fever, dry cough, and dyspnea; less frequent are odynophagia, gastrointestinal symptoms, and anosmia or ageusia. A high proportion of patients develop pneumonia, often bilaterally, and this may lead to respiratory failure and the need for respiratory support in more than 6% of cases. Around 30% will require admission to hospital, and 5% to 10% will need admission to intensive care units (ICUs). Mortality varies widely, from around 2% to somewhat greater than 10% in some countries, and it appears higher in older individuals and those with comorbidities and marked respiratory compromise.

Infection can also occur without symptoms or with very mild symptoms, and patients with these forms are probably potent vectors helping to spread infection.

Recalcati,⁸ who was a dermatologist, observed skin manifestations in 20.4% of a group of 88 patients with COVID-19; in some cases, these manifestations were present from the start whereas others appeared during or after admission to hospital. Hedou et al.,⁹ in response to the aforementioned article, reported skin lesions attributable to COVID-19 in 4.9% of patients with a positive polymerase chain reaction (PCR) test result in a series of 103 patients. However, the real incidence of skin manifestations in infection by SARS-CoV-2 is not known, bearing in mind that at the time, the focus was on patients with severe signs or symptoms, and diagnosis was made in many patients with no or limited symptoms following a telephone call by the patient to the primary care physician, without any face-to-face visits, and therefore no skin examination

Dermatological symptoms in patients with COVID-19 are very diverse; their incidence depends on age, comorbidities and drug treatment of patients. Recalcati S. (2020) observed skin manifestations in 18 (20.4%) of 88 hospitalized patients in northern Italy. He focuses on the fact that 60 (40.5%) out of 148 patients with a positive COVID-19 test who had already taken medications in the previous 15 days were excluded from the study beforehand. Eight (44%) out of 18 patients developed exanthema with the onset of the first clinical symptoms of COVID-19, the rest – after discharge from hospital. Skin manifestations included mainly erythematous rash (14 patients); in three patients, it was in the form of generalized urticaria and vesicles similar to the signs of chickenpox. Overall, skin manifestations were most often located on the torso and were accompanied by slight itching; they disappeared within several days and had no correlation with disease severity. The authors suggested that the abovementioned symptoms were similar to those that develop in cases of conventional viral infections. Marzona A.V. et al. (2020) described a rash similar to chickenpox rash in (54.6%) of 22 patients with COVID-19. All seven patients who underwent skin biopsy showed histological results that corresponded to viral infection.

One also described petechial and reticular rash in patients with COVID-19: almost asymptomatic, accidentally found elements on the mucosa of cheeks, gums, in the vestibule of the oral cavity, on the mucosa of lips. Rash in the form of spots of opal-like color and small, slightly elevated papules with striae on their surface (Wickham striae). Rash similar to livedo, in the form of a tree branch or a fern leaf on hyperemic mucosa. Acro-ischemia: cyanosis of fingers and toes, skin blisters and dry gangrene were described in a number of patients from the Chinese city of Wuhan with severe COVID-19. Some authors reported the development of symptoms resembling frostbite in connection with coronavirus disease (“COVID toes”). Preliminary results of a systematic meta-analysis based on publications from PubMed/MEDLINE and medRxiv databases using the keywords «COVID-19», «2019-nCoV» and «coronavirus» published during the period from December 31, 2019 to May 03, 2020 revealed the following: 46 articles with a total of 998 patients from nine countries met the inclusion criteria declared in these works (confirmed novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19), skin symptoms appeared several days after the first symptoms of COVID-19). A smaller part of these articles contained information on skin manifestations of COVID-19 in more than five patients in the sample.

The most common skin findings were frostbite-like lesions (n = 402, 40.2%), maculopapular lesions (n = 227, 22.7%), urticaria (n = 89, 8.9%), vesicular elements (n = 64, 6.4%), livedoid and necrotic lesions (n = 28, 2.8%), and other undescribed skin elements and lesions (n = 192, 19.8%). Pain and burning were reported in at least 85 (8.5%) cases, and itching – in 256 (25.6%) patients. The prevalence of skin manifestations of COVID-19 ranged from 0.19 to 20.45%

Other Italian authors suggested that exanthema similar to chickenpox was a rare but specific skin manifestation associated with PCR-confirmed coronavirus disease. The authors described a rash that appeared three days after the onset of specific clinical symptoms of COVID-19; it was spread across the torso, of small size, with no itching, and disappeared without scarring after eight days.

Analysis of the currently available literature revealed a limited number of studies on the association of various skin lesions with both COVID-19 and viral infections in

general. However, timely detection and accurate diagnosis of skin manifestations in cases of COVID-19 can play a key role in the early diagnosis and treatment of this disease.

The American Academy of Dermatology, one of the largest dermatological organizations in the world, recently launched the much-needed COVID-19 patient registry to track skin manifestations. Careful documentation and reliable reporting of skin lesions associated with COVID-19 are necessary to improve our understanding of the epidemiology and mechanisms of manifestation of this disease. Timely diagnosis of skin manifestations, comorbidities and improvement of treatment methods will increase the level of high-quality medical care.

Reference:

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